

ASSOCIATION OF COMMUNITY PHARMACIST OF NIGERIA (ACPN)

RIVERS STATE BRANCH

WORLD PHARMACIST DAY 2019 (TEST RESULT)

The theme of this year's World Pharmacists Day, held on September 25, is "Safe and effective medicines for all," according to the International Pharmaceutical Federation (FIP). The theme aims to highlight the key role that pharmacists play in protecting patient safety through improved medicine use and reduced medication errors. "Pharmacists use their broad knowledge and unique expertise to ensure that people get the best from their medicines," said FIP president Dominique Jordan.¹ "We ensure access to medicines and their appropriate use, improve adherence, coordinate care transitions, and so much more. Today, more than ever, pharmacists are charged with the responsibility to ensure that when a patient uses a medicine, it will not cause harm."

Total Number of People Tested - 98

Age	Number		Percentage	
	Male	Female	Male (%)	Female (%)
0 - 12	0	1	0	1.0
13 - 25	1	10	1.0	10.2
26 - 35	6	24	6.1	24.5
36 - 45	8	26	8.2	26.5
46 and Above	8	14	8.2	14.3
Total Number of People Tested	23	75	23.5	76.5

Table 1. Number of People tested according to age range

Figure 1. Number of People tested according to age range

A total of 98 participants enrolled for the various test on the world pharmacist day, 23 (23.5%) were males, while 75 (76.5%) were females, Categorizing participants with age as a criteria, those aged 0 – 12 years, 1 (1%) female participated, 13 -25 years, 1 (1%) Male and 10 (10.2%)

Female, 26 – 35 years, 6 (6.1%) Male and 24 (24.5%) Female, 36 – 45 years, 8 (8.2%) Male and 26 (26.5%) Female while for 46 years and above, 8 (8.2%) Males and 14 (14.3%) Females.

OUTLINE OF THE TOTAL TEST CARRIED OUT ON WORLD PHARMACIST DAY 2019

Figure 7. Outline of the various test, total number of participants and classifications according to guideline.

A total of 94 participants had their blood pressure measured, using the American Heart Association (AHA) classification², 40 (42.6%) of these participants were considered to have a normal blood pressure reading within the range of 12/80 mmHg, 12 (12.8%) had elevated blood pressure readings (120-129/less than 80 mmHg), 18 (19.1%) had high blood pressure (Hypertension Stage 1, 130-139/80-89 mmHg), 18 (19.1%) had High Blood Pressure (Stage 2, 140 or Higher/90 or Higher mmHg) and 6 (6.4%) Participants' can be classified within the range of Hypertensive Crisis (180/Greater than 120 mmHg). 24 participants enrolled for the Random blood sugar test, 22 (91.7%) that enrolled had Normal blood

glucose level (Below 11.1 mmol/L) while 2 (8.3%) had diabetes (11.1 mmol/L and above), although further confirmatory test are needed before a tentative diagnosis could be made.

About 29 Participants were tested for Malaria parasite, 7 (24.1%) tested positive while 22 (75.9%) of the participants that enrolled tested negative. A total of 44 (73.3%) participants out of the 60 questioned were dewormed.

*Percentage was calculated relative to number of participants for a particular test and not total participants.

BLOOD PRESURE MEASUREMENT

The American Heart Association blood pressure ranges was used to classify the blood pressure readings obtained on that day.

BLOOD PRESSURE CATEGORY	SYSTOLIC mm Hg (upper number)		DIASTOLIC mm Hg (lower number)
NORMAL	LESS THAN 120	and	LESS THAN 80
ELEVATED	120 – 129	and	LESS THAN 80
HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE (HYPERTENSION) STAGE 1	130 – 139	or	80 – 89
HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE (HYPERTENSION) STAGE 2	140 OR HIGHER	or	90 OR HIGHER
HYPERTENSIVE CRISIS (consult your doctor immediately)	HIGHER THAN 180	and/or	HIGHER THAN 120

Figure 3. American Heart Association Blood Pressure Ranges.²

Figure 2. Blood Pressure readings and classification according to AHA Blood Pressure Ranges

BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVEL MEASUREMENT

Since Random blood glucose was measured, the National Institute for Clinical Excellence (NICE)³ criteria for diagnosis of diabetes and pre-diabetes was used.

Blood sugar levels in diagnosing diabetes			
Plasma glucose test	Normal	Prediabetes	Diabetes
Random	Below 11.1 mmol/l Below 200 mg/dl	N/A	11.1 mmol/l or more 200 mg/dl or more
Fasting	Below 5.5 mmol/l Below 100 mg/dl	5.5 to 6.9 mmol/l 100 to 125 mg/dl	7.0 mmol/l or more 126 mg/dl or more
2 hour post-prandial	Below 7.8 mmol/l Below 140 mg/dl	7.8 to 11.0 mmol/l 140 to 199 mg/dl	11.1 mmol/l or more 200 mg/dl or more

Figure 4. Criteria for Diabetes Diagnosis (NICE)

Figure 5. Blood Glucose Measurement test result.

MALARIA PARASITE TEST

Figure 6. Malaria Parasite test result

DEWORMING

Figure 7. Participants already dewormed prior to and those dewormed on world pharmacist day 2019

DISCUSSION: Using Age as the demographic classification, participants aged 36-45 had the highest number of participants for all the test carried out on World Pharmacist day. The five blood pressure ranges as recognized by the American Heart Association are: Blood pressure numbers of less than 120/80 mm Hg are considered within the normal range. Elevated blood pressure is when readings consistently range from 120-129 systolic and less than 80 mm Hg diastolic. Hypertension Stage 1 is when blood pressure consistently ranges from 130-139 systolic or 80-89 mm Hg diastolic. Hypertension Stage 2 is when blood pressure consistently ranges at 140/90 mm Hg or higher and Hypertensive crisis, this stage of high blood pressure requires medical attention, blood pressure readings suddenly exceed 180/120 mm Hg.² The blood pressure readings obtained was spread among the different AHA classifications for the Ages and gender.

Understanding blood glucose level ranges can be a key part of diabetes self-management. Recommended blood glucose levels have a degree of interpretation for every individual and should be discussed within the healthcare team. In addition, women may have set target blood sugar levels during pregnancy (pregnancy status of female participants were not captured on that day). For the majority of healthy individuals, normal blood sugar levels are as follows: Between 4.0 to 5.4 mmol/L (72 to 99 mg/dL) when fasting, up to 7.8 mmol/L (140 mg/dL) 2 hours after eating. For people with diabetes, blood sugar level targets are as follows: Before meals: 4 to 7 mmol/L for people with type 1 or type 2 diabetes and after meals: under 9 mmol/L for people with type 1 diabetes and under 8.5mmol/L for people with type 2 diabetes.⁴ The test carried out was random blood glucose level, further test (Fasting blood sugar) should be done before a tentative diabetes diagnosis for those with random blood sugar 11.1 mmol/L and above.

CONCLUSION: Efforts should be made to get more people enrolled during an outreach such as the World Pharmacist Day, From the result obtained, few participants enrolled for other test carried out apart from the blood pressure measurement, whereas a total of 98 participants enrolled for the tests which was supposed to run simultaneously giving every one the opportunity to take all test before being counselled, 94 (95.9%) Participants had their blood pressure readings taken, same cannot be said for Blood Glucose test which had 24 (24.5%) enrolled, Malaria Parasite had 29 (29.6%) take the text and 60 (61.2%) answered questions whether they were dewormed or not. Further testing should be comprehensive and run simultaneously, data properly captured so that a reliable result that can serve as working tool can be obtained.

References

1. International Pharmaceutical Federation (FIP), (25/03/19), <https://www.fip.org/world-pharmacist-day> - accessed 03/10/2019
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3. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence. Type 2 diabetes in adults management, NICE guidelines (NG28), 2017, <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng28>
4. NICE guideline, Type 1 diabetes in adults, diagnosis and management, National Institute for Healthcare and Excellence, August 2015, [nice.org.uk/guidance/ng17](https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng17)